

STAR-ProBio

**Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Bio-based
Products**

Grant Agreement Number 727740

STAR
ProBio

Deliverable D10.1

**Launch and management of
dedicated website and social media**

Version 1.0, 28 July 2017

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Work Programme BB-01-2016: Sustainability schemes for the bio-based economy

www.star-probio.eu

REPORT

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1.0	Final

Abstract

This report describes the work carried out by Unitelma Sapienza in order to be compliant with what foreseen in Task 10.2 (Information and tools sharing through dedicated website and social media) of the STAR-ProBio project and to develop and launch:

A dedicated multilingual website;

Social media to inform stakeholders on the progress of STAR-ProBio.

The main objective of this Deliverable 10.1 is to report on activities undertaken to effectively share information and make available sustainability assessment tools, examples and case studies which will be developed throughout the lifetime of the project.

This is of great importance for keeping stakeholders up to date on events and progress.

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1 Introduction

This report describes the work carried out by Unitelma Sapienza in order to be compliant with what foreseen in Task 10.2 (Information and tools sharing through dedicated website and social media) of the STAR-ProBio project and to develop and launch:

- A dedicated multilingual website;
- Social media to inform stakeholders on the progress of STAR-ProBio.

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2 Registration data

The STAR-ProBio website (www.star-probio.eu) has been registered on the 21st of April 2017.

Below screenshots of all registration data are reported.

WHOIS search: star-probio.eu

star-probio.eu: **Not available for registration**
(What does that mean?)

WHOIS DATA	
Domain name	star-probio.eu
Status	In Use
Registered	21 Apr 2017
Expiry date	21 Apr 2018
Last update	21 Apr 2017
REGISTRAR	
Organisation	Seeweb srl
Website	www.seeweb.com
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inaccurate registrant data Dispute the registration Request an authorisation code 	

REGISTRANT	
For privacy reasons, the registration data of private persons is not fully disclosed. You may request this data under strict conditions by completing a personal data disclosure form: Click here .	
Name	
Organisation	
Language	Italian
Address	
Phone	
Fax	
Email	p.morone@gmail.com

Area Clienti
Benvenuto p.morone@gmail.com

Esci →

- Stato degli ordini
- Topservers
- Apri ticket assistenza
- Visualizza i tuoi ticket
- Fatture e contabilità
- Aggiorna profilo
- Cambia password
- Webmail

Procedure aggiuntive

Dati relativi all'Intestatario del nome a dominio STAR-PROBIO.EU

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Fax:
E-mail: **p.morone@gmail.com**

Codice Fiscale: **MRNPGS76E10A662H**

Società: ---
Partita IVA: ---

Figure 1 Registration Data

3 Design, Maintenance and Updating

The website is managed by Unitelma Sapienza, which developed its graphic design. It provides a feedback mechanism and two different navigation areas (public and private). Unitelma Sapienza administers the website, analysing the web traffic periodically through Google Analytics, in order to measure how users interact with the website content.

A dedicated staff member is updating the website regularly, sharing news, information on events, presentations and relevant studies.

4 Sections

The STAR-ProBio webpage hosts both a public and a private area. The **private area** is designed as a single working platform for partners, External Advisory Board members and key stakeholders. Moreover, the private area is used to share confidential documents. Access to private area requires a login procedure. All partners have been assigned credential (user id and password).

Figure 2 Private Area

The **public area** is designed to ensure public visibility of project's achievements and outcomes. The main sections of the public area are listed below:

- "Home Page"
- "Objectives"
- "WPs"
- "Deliverables"
- "Partners"
- "News"
- "Contact us"

4.1 Home Page

The Home Page provides overall information about the project. This information is currently available in English. By September 2017, it will be made available also in the following languages: French, German, Italian, Polish and Spanish.

Figure 3 Home Page

4.2 Objectives

This section describes STAR-ProBio's main goals, providing a succinct explanation on how the project will achieve them. This information is currently available in English. By September 2017, it will be made available also in the following languages: French, German, Italian, Polish and Spanish.

Figure 4 Objectives

4.3 WPs

This section provides an overall description of the activities the Consortium has to carry out in each WP (as described in the Grant Agreement). This information is currently available in English. By September 2017, it will be made available also in the following languages: French, German, Italian, Polish and Spanish.

Figure 5 WPs

4.4 Deliverables

This page is a knowledge library, enclosing all relevant STAR-ProBio's deliverables and results, assessment tools, presentations, policy documents and minutes of the dissemination events.

Figure 6 Deliverables

4.5 Partners

This section contains a punctual description of each of the fifteen partners of the Consortium, together with the logo and a link to the relative webpage. A list of the members of the External Advisory Board is also included at the end of the page.

Figure 7 Partners

4.6 News

Regular posts on the progresses of the project are published here, along with the newsletter, a dedicated blog, announcements on the dissemination events, useful links to other relevant information sources and projects.

Figure 8 News

4.7 Contact Us

Figure 9 Contact Us

5 Social Media

In addition to the website, social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter) are important tools to reach out to, and inform stakeholders on the progress of STAR-ProBio.

Social media are regularly updated by a dedicated staff member, with news, web streaming, pictures, events etc.

Links to Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter have been included in the STAR-ProBio webpage.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 727740.

The STAR-ProBio logo was kindly designed by www.edondesign.net.

Figure 10 Social Media

6 Statistics

The web-site records 207 sessions over the time-frame 01-06-2017 / 09-07-2017: 188 via a direct connection; 14 via the Google search engine; 2 via the Bing search engine; 1 via the Facebook social network. The greater amount of connections (188) comes from direct hits because the search engines (16 results) are still indexing the web-pages and processing their meta-data. The search engine optimization (SEO) should take effect around the beginning of the next year.

Figure 11 Statistics

The most contacted page is the Home (167 sessions), the site shows a returning visitors records around 70% and a geographical distribution spanning from the EU to North America.

Figure 12 Statistics

Finally, the navigation tree shows a good interaction rate within the site from the Home with the first 3 interactions recording a low bounce-out rate (visitors who abandon from the site).

Figure 13 Statistics